

New European Bauhaus Academy

Eyes Hearths Hands: The NEB Urban Revolution

1st New European Bauhaus Academy Conference

Barcelona, February 27, 2026

Carlo Battisti
Living Future Europe

Circular Bio-based Europe

Joint Undertaking

EYES HEARTS HANDS URBAN REVOLUTION

LIVING FUTURE
EUROPE

EHHUR AMONG THE FIRST NEB LIGHTHOUSE DEMONSTRATORS

BoSS
Bauhaus of the
Seas Sails

CULTUURCAMPUS
a sustainable hub of arts, research,
learning and community as catalyst

DESIRE
Designing the Irresistible
Circular Society

EHHUR
Eyes Hearts Hands
Urban Revolution

NEBourhoods
Creating NEBourhoods
Together

NEB-STAR
New European Bauhaus
STAvangeR

THREE ELEMENTS TO MAKE CHANGE HAPPEN:

EYES

Aesthetically viable and socially accepted urban transformation

HEARTS

Inclusive and socially fair involvement of local communities

HANDS

Concrete engagement actions for full sustainability

DSS TOOL WORKFLOW

ADAPTATION OF TECHNICAL RENOVATION SOLUTIONS TO LHS

EHHUR Final Event 2025 in Copenhagen

LH5 Izmir (Turkey) - Albayrack Passage

PROCUREMENT TENSION

RISK MINIMISATION

MANAGED EXPERIMENTATION

LH3 Zoersel (Belgium) - Sint-Antonius Library

LH1 Høje-Taastrup (Denmark) - Gadehavegaard district

LH7 Nepi (Italy) - Biodistretto

Scannerizzami

Collegati

PROGETTO EHHUR - EYES HEARTS HANDS - URBAN REVOLUTION
Finanziato dalla Commissione Europea nell'ambito del programma New Bauhaus Horizon Europe - Grant Agreement N.101079948

PUNTO DI RICARICA GRATUITO

Questa struttura ospita un impianto fotovoltaico con pannelli e batterie d'accumulo. Un impianto indipendente dalla rete. Il suo uso è aperto a cittadinanza e ai visitatori. Mentre caricate i vostri dispositivi elettronici, inquadrare il QR Code per celebrare il momento in cui usate energia sostenibile. Grazie per aver contribuito a decarbonizzare il nostro territorio, ogni gesto, apparentemente piccolo, è importante!
A presto!

CE
124
0 24
X046 16
0797

LH4 Maia (Portugal) – Sobreiro district

NOT AMBITION
INSTITUTIONAL DESIGN

PROCUREMENT REFORM

LH6 Osijek (Croatia) – urban regeneration

2. Izmjena Poziva

Financira
Europska unija

SAŽETAK

Poziv na dodjelu bespovratnih sredstava

„ITU - Sportsko - rekreativna i zelena infrastruktura UA Osijek“

Urbana aglomeracija Osijek

referentni broj: IP.3.1.33

Otvoreni postupak u modalitetu trajnog Poziva

Ovaj poziv se financira iz Europskog fonda
za regionalni razvoj

EYES HEARTS HANDS
URBAN REVOLUTION

EHHUR at the NEB Festival 2024

The "600-Year Office" (Gensler)

FRAMEWORK

A structural framework with an extremely long lifespan makes it possible for the rest of the building to be constructed from lightweight, reusable components and materials.

OFFICE

On day 1, the building is primarily office use - the 12m high modules of the framework are divided into three office levels with a 4m floor to floor height.

RESIDENTIAL

Future residential uses can be accommodated at higher density by dividing the 12m height into four 3m levels.

OTHER USES

The 12m floor to floor height of the fundamental framework allows almost any amenity or other use.

Lateral stability is achieved largely via sheer walls, which allows the core to be as flexible as possible.

Facade elements are made from 100% reusable, upgradable components

CLT floor slab components in the lightweight 'insets' can be easily reconfigured or reused, unlike concrete floor slabs.

CAPACITY IS INFRASTRUCTURE

ADVANCE TO THE NEXT LEVEL

INSTITUTIONAL EVOLUTION